

A Comparative Analysis of Noise Reduction in Sound Signals using Wavelet Transformation and Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)

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Abstract – In a communication system, when sending an information signal from the sender to the receiver, the signal will be mixed with other unwanted signals. The unwanted signal is called noise. One form of information signal is a sound signal. Random sound signal. The pattern or characteristics of the signal will change from the original if the sound signal contains noise. The more noise it contains, the more the pattern changes. Therefore, a method is needed to reduce the noise contained in the voice signal before it is estimated. In this study, we will compare the wavelet transform and fast Fourier transform (FFT) methods to reduce noise in voice signals. From the test results, the Wavelet Transform method was obtained using Soft Threshold using Mother Wavelet Coilet 5, which gave the best performance; noise was completely eliminated; and the smallest information signal that was eliminated was 8.1606 Watt or 9.117 dBW compared to other Mother Wavelets. Meanwhile, with FFT, noise that is spread over the entire frequency range cannot be completely eliminated.

Keywords: Wavelet, FFT and SNR

Introduction

In a communication system, the effectiveness of disseminating information from the sender (i.e., the transmitter) to the receiver (i.e., the recipient) is contingent upon the degree of precision with which the receiver is capable of receiving the transmitted signal. In actuality, it is commonplace for the information signal received by the recipient to be damaged or inaccurate. Noise, in fact, is responsible for the majority of transmission errors that occur within communication systems. Noise can prove to be disruptive in three key areas of communication systems :

- 1) Noise causes the listener to not understand the original signal being conveyed or even the entire signal.
- 2) Noise can cause failure in the signal reception system.
- 3) Noise makes the system inefficient.

Noise and distortion are the primary factors that constrain the data transmission capacity in communication systems, alongside their impact on the precision of signal measurement systems. Therefore, the modeling and removal of noise and distortion must be the central concern from both theoretical and practical perspectives in communication systems and signal processing. The reduction of noise and removal of distortion are significant challenges in various applications, including mobile cellular systems, communications, speech recognition, image processing, medical signal processing, radar, sonar, and other applications where the desired signals are inevitably intertwined with noise and distortion.

Various techniques are utilized for reducing noise, including the fast Fourier transform and wavelet transform. Diverse investigations have been conducted to eliminate noise signals from voice signals, one of which is Nurul Hidayat's research, dubbed "Applications of Wavelet Transformation in Voice Signal Processing" [1]. The study involved testing different voices that had been recorded with a microphone, to

which noise was added at varying levels for simulation purposes. Despite the fact that the wavelet transform cannot quantitatively eliminate noise entirely, the denoising application works satisfactorily and generates a sound signal that is nearly identical to the initial signal.

A further investigation was carried out by Asyur Zaldi, with the title "Diminishing Noise from Sound Signals through Wavelet Package Transformation featuring Coif 4 as the Wavelet Function" [2]. Gaussian noise is deliberately introduced into the sound signal at multiple levels for the purpose of simulation in this study. For the purpose of noise reduction, the Coif 4 mother wavelet is employed in conjunction with soft thresholding. The decomposition process yields a diminutive MSE value at level 4.

Another study was conducted by Dedy Darmadi, entitled "Simulation of Noise Elimination Using the Wavelet Transformation Method Assisted by Matlab's Graphical User Interface (GUI)." [3]. In this study, noise was eliminated with the wavelet transform, and the simulation process was carried out with the help of the GUI in Matlab. From the simulation results, it is obtained that the higher the decomposition level used, the higher the SNR value obtained; however, the higher the risk of loss of signal information in the sound file is eliminated, and the Cioflet wavelet type gets better results for each sound sample.

Muhammad Satria Adhi conducted a study titled "Simulation of Noise Elimination in Sound Signals Using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) Method" [4]. The study has been designed to investigate the removal of voices that have been mixed with noise utilizing FFT. To this end, FFT has been employed in order to display the spectrum of the speech signal and filter spectrum while also setting the filter cut-off frequency. It is noteworthy that any signal whose frequency is above the cut-off frequency of the filter is deemed as noise and shall be eliminated.

In this study, we will compare the wavelet transform and fast Fourier transform (FFT) methods for reducing noise in sound. The parameter to be analyzed here is the signal-to-noise ratio after the reduction process, based on the results of using the two methods.

Basic Theory

Audio Signal

Audio is a term used to refer to the sound or reproduction of sound. Audio signals, also known as sound waves, are waves that arise from the vibration of an object within the audio frequency range, which can be heard by human beings. Within the confines of an audio signal, the human ear has the capacity to detect sounds ranging from 20 Hz to 20 KHz (20,000 Hz). Fundamentally, the audio signal is one that is discernible by the human ear. The number 20 Hz is the lowest sound frequency that can be heard, while 20 KHz is the highest frequency that can be heard.

Sound waves are subject to variations due to changes in the pressure of a medium, such as air. Sound is generated by an object's vibration, which induces corresponding vibrations in the surrounding air. These resultant air vibrations, in turn, cause the human eardrum to vibrate, ultimately resulting in the perception of sound by the brain. The production of sound waves by a speaker is depicted in Figure 1. These waves propagate through the air, and the black dots in the aforementioned image signify air molecules. The speaker's vibrations cause the adjacent air molecules to vibrate in specific patterns, which are represented by waveforms. These vibrations of air molecules result in the listener's eardrum vibrating in the same pattern.

Figure 1. Sound waves

Noise

Noise is an undesired signal that persistently appears in a transmission system. It has an adverse effect on the quality of the received signal and the reproduction of the transmitted signal. Moreover, it can curtail the range of the system at a certain transmit power, impact the sensitivity of the reception signal, and lead to a reduction in the system's bandwidth. Noise is classified into two categories, internal noise and external noise, based on its origin. The former is generated by the communication system's components, such as thermal noise. The latter, on the other hand, is caused outside the electronic circuits of the communication system, for instance, atmospheric noise. Atmospheric noise can be triggered by natural phenomena, such as lightning, thunder, and storms, among others.

Signal to Noise Ratio

In order to detect an information signal in a receiving system, it is necessary that the power of the desired signal exceeds the prevailing noise disturbance. The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), which is frequently used to describe the ratio of the desired signal power to noise power, can be formulated according to [5].

$$\frac{S}{N} (dB) = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{The desired signal power}}{\text{power of the noise}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Wavelet Transform

The development of wavelet transform comprises two distinct series, namely the continuous wavelet transform (CWT) and the discrete wavelet transform (DWT). The functions employed in both the CWT and DWT transformations are obtained from the mother wavelet by means of translation, shift, and scaling or compression. The coefficients and definition of DWT are explicitly outlined as per [6] :

$$W_f(s, \tau) = \langle f(t), \Psi_{s,\tau}(t) \rangle = \int f(t) \Psi_{s,\tau}^*(t) dt \quad (2)$$

Where $f(t)$ is a signal in the time domain, $\Psi_{s,\tau}(t)$ is a wavelet and $*$ denotes a complex conjugation.

When the function $f(t)$ is subjected to a series of filters derived from a wavelet family, the resultant output is known as the DWT (Discrete Wavelet Transform) coefficient. These coefficients serve to characterize the content of the function in the time-scale domain. In the case of the two-channel diskrit wavelet transform, the function is segregated into lowpass and highpass components [6], as illustrated in Figure 2(a). The filter $h(k)$ functions as a scaling filter, or lowpass filter, while $g(k)$ serves as a wavelet filter, or highpass filter.

The next step is to transform the approximation coefficient $cA1$ into two parts using the same scheme, replacing $cA1$ and producing $cA2$ and $cD2$, and so on. For higher levels, the approximation coefficients are further decomposed into approximation coefficients and detail coefficients at the next level. Figure 2(b) illustrates the decomposition of DWT filter banks at level 3.

The process of decomposition involves the application of both low pass filter (LPF) and high pass filter (HPF), which are utilized for horizontal filtering and downsampling. Subsequently, a reconstruction process is executed to retrieve the original signal from the approximations and detailed components. The objective of the reconstruction process is to integrate all detail components with approximation components. This process is illustrated in Figure 2(c) [6].

Figure 2. Wavelet Transform process.

The employment of the wavelet transform involves the use of the mother wavelet, which serves as the fundamental function. The mother wavelet is responsible for generating all the wavelet functions that are utilized in the transformation process via translation and scaling. As such, the mother wavelet is crucial in determining the characteristics of the resulting wavelet transform. Consequently, meticulous documentation of the wavelet's application is required, and an appropriate selection of the mother wavelet is imperative to ensure optimal utilization of the wavelet transform. The Haar, Daubechies, Coiflet, and Symlet mother wavelets are the focus of this study's examination.

Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)

The Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is a computational procedure, designed for the efficient and expeditious computation of the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT). Its widespread and extensive application is observed across diverse domains, ranging from digital signal processing to the resolution of partial differential equations and intricate algorithms for the multiplication of large integers.

For example, $x_0, \dots, x_{N-1}$, are complex numbers. The discrete Fourier transform is defined by the formula [7]:

$$X_k = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x_n e^{-\frac{2\pi}{N}nk} \quad k = 0, \dots, N-1 \quad (3)$$

DFT calculations directly require arithmetic operations of $O(N^2)$ or have order N^2 . An FFT algorithm only requires $O(N \log N)$ operations to compute the same series. In general, these algorithms depend on N -factoring. The earliest and therefore most popular FFT algorithm is the Cooley-Tukey algorithm.

Research Metodologi

In this research, the noise reduction process will be carried out on voice signals using two methods, namely the wavelet transform and the fast Fourier transform (FFT). The steps in this research are as follows:

- 1) Record the sound signal, then convert the sound signal into "wav" format.
- 2) Next, read the sound signal using the Matlab software.
- 3) Next, the sound signal is added with AWGN noise, and the noise level is varied.
- 4) Next, the noise reduction process is carried out using two methods, namely the wavelet transform and the fast Fourier transform (FFT).
- 5) After the noise reduction process is carried out, the signal-to-noise ratio of the reduced signal is then calculated.

The entire research process is described in the flowchart in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Flowchart for Researchs.

Figure 4. The results of noise reduction using wavelet transform (soft thresholding).

Analysis and Discussion

In the present investigation, the coveted information signal takes the form of a vocal signal. The auditory signal is captured by means of a sound recording application on a portable computer, and its format is subsequently transformed into wav. Moreover, the recorded signal is subjected to Gaussian noise which is

generated by means of Matlab. Consequent to this, the noise reduction procedure will be evaluated utilizing the wavelet transform and the fast Fourier transform (FFT) methods.

In the simulation of the noise reduction process using the wavelet transform, there are 4 mother wavelets to be tested, namely Haar, Daubechies 12, Coiflet 5, and Symlet 8. The decomposition level to be tested is level ten. The thresholds being tested are hard thresholding and soft thresholding. Then the value of the signal-to-noise ratio will be calculated for the signal that has been reduced to noise.

1.) Soft Threshold

For the results of noise reduction testing using a soft threshold, Haar wavelet mother, coiflet 5 wavelet mother, Daubechies 12 wavelet mother and Symlet 8 wavelet mothers, and a decomposition level of 10, the graph can be seen in Figure 4 (a), (b), (c) and (d).

In the noise reduction process using Soft Threshold with a decomposition level of 10, noise is completely eliminated, but not only noise is eliminated; there are also information signals that are also eliminated. From the results of the four Mother Wavelet tests, using Mother Wavelet Haar, the information power that was eliminated was 18.2537 Watt or 12.613 dBW; for Mother Wavelet Coiflet 5, the information power that was eliminated was 8.1606 Watt or 9.117 dBW; for Mother Wavelet Daubechies 12, the information power that was eliminated was 10.6211 Watt or 10.26169 dBW; and for Mother Wavelet Symlet 8, the information power that was also eliminated was 9.6976 Watt or 9.866 dBW. The smallest information power that is eliminated is using Mother Wavelet Coiflet 5. Based on subjective criteria, using Soft Threshold, Mother Wavelet Coiflet 5 produces the best performance.

2.) Hard Threshold

For the results of the noise reduction test using the Hard Threshold, using the Haar wavelet mother, coiflet 5 wavelet mother, Daubechies 12 wavelet mother and Symlet 8 wavelet mothers and the decomposition level used being level 10, the graph can be seen in Figure 5 (a), (b), (c) and (d).

Figure 5. The results of noise reduction using wavelet transform (hard thresholding).

Simulation performance is measured by objective and subjective criteria. For objective criteria through hearing and sound signal graphics. As for the subjective assessment, it is the signal-to-noise ratio, or SNR, in the denoised sound signal. While the parameters tested were threshold type, mother wavelet type, and decomposition level, The SNR value data from the simulation results using the hard threshold can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Signal To Noise Ratio (SNR) Value of Simulation Results for Each Mother Wavelet and Hard Threshold

Wavelet	Threshold	Decomposition Levels	SNR	SNR(dB)
Haar	Hard	10	58.4428	17.6673
Coiflet 5	Hard	10	28.6708	14.5744
Daubechies 12	Hard	10	36.4778	15.6203
Symlet 8	Hard	10	51.2646	17.0982

In the noise reduction process using Hard Threshold with a decomposition level of 10, the highest SNR value was obtained using Mother Wavelet Haar with SNR = 58.4428, or 17.6673 dB. Based on subjective criteria, using the Hard Threshold, Mother Wavelet Haar gives the best performance.

Noise Reduction Process Using Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)

In the noise reduction process using the FFT, a graphic of the recorded sound and its spectrum will first be displayed, as can be seen in Figure 6 (a). Then the recorded sound is added to Gaussian noise. The sound signal is mixed with noise, and its spectrum can be seen in Figure 6 (b).

Figure 6. Sound signal and Its spectrum denoising results using FFT with window Hamming.

In the noise reduction process using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), the sound signal's spectrum is displayed to determine its frequency. From the spectrum display, it can be seen the frequency of the sound signal, so that the cut-off frequency can be determined for the filtering process. In displaying the spectrum using FFT. Gaussian noise is spread over all frequency ranges. The filtering process here uses a low-pass FIR digital filter, which is designed using the window method. The graph of the noise signal and the spectrum that has been removed using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) and Hamming window can be seen in Figure 6 (c). The signal-to-noise ratio for the filtered output signal is 55.35, and the SNR in dB is 17.43 dB.

Apart from Window Hamming, the other windows that will be tested are Rectangular, Hanning, and Blackman. SNR values for other window test results can be seen in Table 2 below:

Table 2. SNR Values from Simulation Results Using FFT for Each Window

Window	SNR	SNR(dB)
Hamming	55.35	17.43
Rectangular	94.857	19.77
Hanning	48.649	16.87
Blackman	58.31	17.657

Comparative Analysis of Noise Reduction Results Using Wavelet Transform and FFT

Noise is spread evenly in all frequency ranges. In the noise reduction process using the wavelet transform, noise is removed by denoising the signal in the time and frequency domains simultaneously. The process of removing noise is done by determining the threshold value. In the noise reduction process using the wavelet transform, the parameters that can be changed in the test are:

- 1) The type of mother wavelet

Here the author tested the mother wavelets Haar, Daubechies 12, Coiflet 5, and Symlet 8.

- 2) Threshold Types

Namely soft threshold and hard threshold Determining the threshold value is very influential in determining the results.

- 3) Level of Decomposition

In the process of reducing noise through the implementation of FFT, the noise removal procedure is executed within the frequency domain. In order to effectively filter the signal from the noise, it is imperative that the spectrum of the signal be presented beforehand. Upon analysis of this spectrum, the cutoff frequency of the filter can be ascertained. Since noise is uniformly disseminated throughout the entire frequency range, it is impossible to eliminate noise below the filter's cutoff frequency. It is only plausible to remove noise that exists beyond the cutoff frequency of the filter. In order to conduct tests on the digital FIR filter, designed using the window method, it is utilized.

In the realm of voice signal noise reduction, particularly in the case of Gaussian noise that permeates all spectral frequencies, the wavelet transform surpasses the Fourier transform. The wavelet transform is capable of complete noise removal, while a residue of noise remains present when employing the FFT. The simulation results indicate that the wavelet transform accompanied by a mother coefficient of 5 and a soft threshold offers optimal performance. In the process of noise reduction through wavelet transform, the soft threshold implementation leads to the elimination of the information signal; however, the mother wavelet coefficient of 5 results in the elimination of the least amount of information signal.

Conclusion

From the data obtained from the simulation results, it can be concluded:

1. For the purpose of noise reduction, particularly in cases involving Gaussian noise, the wavelet transform has been shown to offer superior performance in comparison to the fast Fourier transform. This is due to the fact that Gaussian noise is evenly distributed across all frequency ranges.
2. The simulation outcomes reveal that the implementation of Soft Threshold in the wavelet transformation for noise reduction yields the most optimal performance. By employing Mother Wavelet Coiflet 5, noise can be entirely eliminated while minimizing the removal of the smallest

information signal in contrast to other mother wavelets. Specifically, this equates to a reduction of 8.1606 Watts or 9,117 dBW.

3. For the noise reduction process using FFT, using a digital FIR filter designed with the window method, the highest SNR value is obtained from the results of using a rectangular window, namely $SNR = 94.857$ or 19.77 dB.

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